

DIAGNOSTIC ACCURACY OF ABC SCORING SYSTEM IN PREDICTING OUTCOME IN PATIENTS WITH UPPER GASTROINTESTINAL BLEEDING

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Abstract

Objectives: To determine diagnostic accuracy of ABC scoring system in predicting outcome in patients with upper gastrointestinal bleeding keeping mortality or repeated episode of upper gastrointestinal bleed in 30 days as gold standard.

Study design: Cross-sectional validation study.

Place and Duration of the study: Ayub Teaching Hospital, Abbottabad from February 2024 to August 2024.

Methodology: A total of 148 patients with upper gastrointestinal bleed were included and their ABC score was assessed. All the patients were followed up for 30 days to document any adverse outcome in the form of mortality and repeat episode bleeding of upper gastrointestinal tract. Based on this diagnostic accuracy parameters were calculated.

Results: In this study, 148 patients were included. Median age was 46.00 (17.00) years. There were 94 (63.50%) male and 54 (36.50%) female patients. 87 (58.80%) patients had variceal bleeding while 61 (41.20%) patients had non-variceal bleeding. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value and accuracy of ABC scoring system in predicting 30-day mortality and repeated episode of upper GI bleed in 30 days were 93.94% & 89.47%, 45.22% & 45.45%, 32.98% & 36.17%, 96.30% & 92.59% and 56.08% & 56.76%, respectively.

Conclusion: ABC score is an effective tool for predicting outcome in patients with upper gastrointestinal bleeding.

INTRODUCTION

Upper gastrointestinal bleeding (UGIB) is a medical emergency characterized by stools colored like black tar (melena), vomitus containing blood (hematemesis) and impairment of the hemodynamic parameters. ¹ The incidence of this condition is highly variable and ranges from 15 to 172 per 100,000 individuals each year and can be classified as acute, sub-acute or obscure bleeding of upper

gastrointestinal tract. ² The chance of developing an upper gastrointestinal bleed is increased by the use of medicines such as aspirin, P2Y12 inhibitors, direct oral anti-coagulants and vitamin K antagonists. ^{3, 4} In addition, the rupture or erosion of esophageal varices, fundal varices, gastric ulcers or erosions and duodenal ulcers are all part of the pathophysiology of upper gastrointestinal bleeding. ⁵ It has been found

that prevalence of upper GI bleed based on the cause ranged from 3.9%-65%.⁶

Endoscopic intervention, more specifically upper GI endoscopy, is the central tenet of the management of bleeding in the upper gastrointestinal tract.⁷ When it comes to assessment of patients of upper GI bleed regarding their prognostic outcome, several scoring systems are developed and used including Rockall, AIMS65 and Glasgow Blatchford score.⁸ Other than these a new scoring system has been developed that is still undergoing extensive research to determine its diagnostic accuracy for predicting outcome in patients with upper gastrointestinal bleeding which is ABC scoring system. In this instance a study reported the values of diagnostic accuracy parameters including sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV) and negative predictive value (NPV) of ABC score in predicting 30-day mortality were 52%, 88%, 25% and 96%, respectively.⁹ On the other hand, another study reported sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV of ABC score in predicting 30-day mortality and repeat episode of upper GI bleed within 30 days were 90%, 86%, 14.6% and 99.7%, respectively and 36.3%, 86.4%, 23.6% and 92.1%, respectively.¹⁰

As evident from the results of the previous studies, diagnostic accuracy of ABC scoring system in predicting outcome in patients with upper gastrointestinal bleeding is highly variable. Also, owing to its nature of being newly opted to be used in clinical settings makes it imperative to further conduct a study to determine diagnostic accuracy of ABC scoring system in predicting outcome in patients with upper gastrointestinal bleeding.

METHODOLOGY

This cross-sectional validation study was conducted at Medicine department, Ayub Teaching Hospital, Abbottabad from February -2024 to August 2024 after getting approval from research evaluation unit (REU) of College of Physicians and Surgeons, (CPSP), Pakistan (Ref No: CPSP/REU/MED-2021-029-17268). Sample size calculation was performed using sensitivity and specificity sample size calculator. Sample size calculation was performed by using confidence level of 95%, precision of 10%, prevalence of 65%⁷, expected sensitivity of 52% and

expected specificity of 88%.¹³ This gave a sample size of 148. Study sample was selected by using non-probability consecutive sampling technique.

All patients aged 18-80 years, of either male or female genders, who presented with upper GI bleed were included. Those who were mentally incapacitated to be part of study and those using anti-coagulant medication and develop bleeding due to abnormal INR (> 3) were excluded.

In all these patients, after initial resuscitation and intervention to stop the bleed, ABC score of all the included patients were documented in the self-made proforma pre-approved by REU CPSP. Based on the ABC score, patients were labeled as either low risk for 30-days mortality and repeat episode of upper GI bleed within 30 days (score < 8) and high risk (score \geq 8). After this, baseline characteristics including age, gender, cause of upper GI bleed, alcohol intake status, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) intake status, smoking status and history of previous such episode were documented. All these patients were then followed up for 30 days to document any adverse outcome in the form of death and/or repeat episode of upper GI bleed. Based on this patients cases were labeled as true positive (TP), true negative (TN), false positive (FP) and false negatives (FN).

TP were patients who had high risk of 30-days mortality or repeated episode of upper GI bleed within 30 days predicted on ABC score and they died or had repeat episode of upper GI bleed within 30 days. TN were patients who had low risk of 30-days mortality or repeated episode of upper GI bleed within 30 days predicted on ABC score and they did not die or had repeat episode of upper GI bleed within 30 days. FP were patients who had high risk of 30-days mortality or repeated episode of upper GI bleed within 30 days predicted on ABC score and they did not die or had repeat episode of upper GI bleed within 30 days. FN were patients who had low high risk of 30-days mortality or repeated episode of upper GI bleed within 30 days predicted on ABC score and they died or had repeat episode of upper GI bleed within 30 days.

Data was analyzed by using Statistical Package for Social Sciences software version 26. Age was found to be not distributed normally upon assessment by using Shapiro-Wilk test and was thus represented

using median interquartile range (IQR). Qualitative variables (gender, cause of upper GI bleed, alcohol intake status, NSAIDs intake status, smoking status and history of previous such episode) were presented as frequency and percentage. 2×2 table was drawn in

order to determine calculate the diagnostic accuracy parameters, using standard formulae, of ABC scoring system in predicting outcome in patients with upper gastrointestinal bleeding.

RESULTS

In this study, 148 patients were included. Median age was 46.00 (17.00) years. There were 94 (63.50%) male and 54 (36.50%) female patients. Among all cases, 87 (58.80%) patients had variceal bleeding while 61 (41.20%) patients had non-variceal

bleeding. In these patients, 67 (45.30%) patients consumed alcohol, 69 (46.60%) patients used NSAIDs, 48 (32.40%) patients were smokers and 28 (18.90%) patients had history of previous episode of UGIB. Baseline parameters of the patients in Table-I:

Table-I: Baseline parameters of the patients (n = 148)

Parameter	Median (IQR); n (%)
Age	46.00 (17.00) years
Gender	
Male	94 (63.50%)
Female	54 (36.50%)
Cause of upper GI bleed	
Variceal	87 (58.80%)
Non-variceal	61 (41.20%)
Alcohol consumption	67 (45.30%)
NSAIDs use	69 (46.60%)
Smoking	48 (32.40%)
History of previous episode of UGIB	28 (18.90%)

Figure 1: Baseline parameter of Patients

Among patients who were at high risk of 30-day mortality (n = 94), 31 (33.00%) died within 30 days (TP) and 63 (67.00%) did not die within 30 days (FP) while among patients who were at low risk of 30-day mortality (n = 54), 2 (3.70%) died within 30 days

(FN) and 52 (96.30%) did not die within 30 days (TN). Based on this, diagnostic accuracy parameters of ABC scoring system in predicting 30-day mortality were calculated given in Table-II:

Table-II: Diagnostic accuracy parameters of ABC scoring system in predicting 30-day mortality (n = 148)

Accuracy	56.08%
Sensitivity	93.94%
Specificity	45.22%
PPV	32.98%
NPV	96.30%

Figure 2: Diagnostics Accuracy parameters of ABC Scoring System and their 30 days repeated episode of upper of Bleed.

Among patients who were at high risk of repeated episode of upper GI bleed in 30 days (n = 94), 34 (36.20%) had repeated episode of upper GI bleed in 30 days (TP) and 60 (63.80%) did not had repeated episode of upper GI bleed in 30 days (FP) while among patients who were at low risk of repeated episode of upper GI bleed in 30 days (n = 54), 4

(7.40%) had repeated episode of upper GI bleed in 30 days (FN) and 50 (92.60%) did not had repeated episode of upper GI bleed in 30 days (TN). Based on this, diagnostic accuracy parameters of ABC scoring system in predicting repeated episode of upper GI bleed in 30 days are given in Table-III:

Table-III: Diagnostic accuracy parameters of ABC scoring system in predicting repeated episode of upper GI bleed in 30 days (n = 148)

Accuracy	56.76%
Sensitivity	89.47%
Specificity	45.45%
PPV	36.17%
NPV	92.59%

Figure 3: Diagnostic Accuracy Parameters of ABC Scoring System

DISCUSSION

UGIB is primarily divided into two major types based on the etiological mechanism resulting in this potentially catastrophic event. These include bleed from the abnormally enlarged vasculature in the esophageal lumen or from the erosion of ulcer present in the stomach mucosa.^{11, 12} A patient presenting with this condition needs a careful and comprehensive evaluation to evaluating the severity of bleed and determining the overall prognosis of the ailing patient. For this purpose, various clinical scoring systems exist.^{13, 14} However, a much simpler score have recently been developed named ABC score that has been considered highly reliable¹⁵ and was the focus of present study.

In this study, average age of the patients who presented with UGIB was 49 years and 63.50% of

those patients were male. This male predominance in cases of UGIB demonstrated in present stated is similar to what has been reported in research work of Manko et al.¹⁶ who found that ratio of males to females cases of UGIB was 2.7 to 1. Similarly, in another study conducted by Alruzug et al.¹⁷ also reported this predominance of males for developing UGIB. This male predominance can be attributed to generally higher indulgence of male population in consumption of certain substances like tobacco, pain killers and alcohol. Most of the cases of UGIB were caused by the bleeding from the varices while lesser number of UGIB cases were non-variceal. One of the reason for this higher frequency of UGIB cases being variceal can be attributed to the rising burden of cirrhotic liver disease secondary to chronic viral hepatitis, particularly hepatitis C, in Pakistan.^{18, 19}

In this study, amongst patients who presented with UGIB, a large proportion of patients had a positive history of consumption of alcohol, regular user of NSAIDs, smoking and history of previous episode of UGIB. All the factors have been reported to increase the risk of developing UGIB. 20, 21

When it comes to diagnostic accuracy parameters of ABC scoring system in predicting 30-day mortality it was observed that its sensitivity was 93.94%, specificity was 45.22%, PPV was 32.98%, NPV was 96.30% and overall accuracy was 56.08%. Additionally, the values of these diagnostic accuracy parameters of ABC scoring system in predicting repeated episode of upper GI bleed in 30 days were 89.47%, 45.45%, 36.17%, 92.59% and 56.76%. Compared to this, a study was conducted by Laursen et al. ⁹ in which it was found that the sensitivity of ABC score to predict the chances of mortality within thirty days after UGIB was only 52% while specificity value was 88% exhibiting that ABC score is specific rather than a sensitive score in this regard which is opposite to the trend of present study. In another study conducted by Sakong et al. ¹⁰ it was found similar to present study, ABC score was highly sensitive score for predicting 30-days mortality but contrary to current study, they found it to be a specific rather than a sensitive score for predicting repeated episode of UGIB. The exact cause of this difference could not be assessed but possible reasons can either be the difference in sample sizes between studies and the differences in the study environment and setting. Similarly, in another study conducted by Saade et al. ²², ABC score was found to be highly useful for predicting the chances of death after UGIB within thirty days.

Present study indicates ABC scoring system is highly sensitive to predict mortality as well as recurrence of UGIB within 30-days period and thus can be used as a reliable tool in this regard. However, due to lack of specificity, it is recommended to use this scoring system in conjunction with other clinical score to improve the accuracy of prediction of 30-days mortality and recurrence of UGIB.

LIMITATIONS

None.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, ABC scoring system is highly sensitive to predict mortality as well as recurrence of UGIB within 30-days period among patients presenting with UGIB.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None.

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